

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins Part IV.* Synthesis of Alkyl-psoralenes

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7-Acyloxy-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin on Fries migration, afforded 7-hydroxy-6-acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin, which on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate, followed by hydrolysis and subsequent cyclisation yielded 4-alkyl or aryl-4',8-alkylpsoralenes (I).

In recent years linear furocoumarins such as psoralene, xanthotoxin etc., have received considerable attention on account of their therapeutic properties. Xanthotoxin is a fish-poison¹. These are also used in the treatment of leukoderma². The most recent application has made the use of the fact that it alters the erythermal response to ultra-violet light, a property which has been used clinically to prevent sun-burns^{3,4}. Kaufmann⁵ has reported the synthesis of psoralene derivatives having alkyl substituents in 5' and 8-positions.** It has been reported by Pathak *et al.*⁶ that properly located alkyl groups do not decrease the activity of psoralene appreciably and particularly that 4,5',8-trimethyl psoralene is as active as psoralene in producing an erythermal response on guinea pigs skin irradiated by ultra-violet light. We report here the synthesis of alkyl and aryl psoralene derivatives having substituents in 4,4' and 8-positions of U.V. Spectra recorded in Table VI to study the relationship between the structure and photodynamic activity of these compounds.

Ia :	$R_1 = -CH_3$,	$R = Ph$
b :	$R_1 = -C_2H_5$,	$R = Ph$
c :	$R_1 = -C_6H_5$,	$R = Ph$
d :	$R_1 = -CH_3$,	$R = CH_3$
e :	$R_1 = -C_2H_5$,	$R = CH_3$
f :	$R_1 = -C_6H_5$,	$R = CH_3$

* Part III, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 649.

** The nomenclature used in this paper is according to A. C. Curtius, *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1959, **32**, 133.

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4. M. A. Pathak and J. H. Fellman, *Nature*, 1960, **185**, 382.
5. K. D. Kaufmann, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 117.
6. M. A. Pathak, J. B. Fellmann and K. D. Kaufmann, *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1960, **35**, 165.

Pechmann condensation of 2-methyl resorcinol with ethyl benzoyl acetate yielded 7-hydroxy-4-phenyl-8-methyl-coumarin, which on acetylation, followed by Fries migration afforded 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin. This when condensed with ethyl-bromoacetate gave ethyl-6-acetyl-4-phenyl-8-methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetate, which on hydrolysis and subsequent cyclisation with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave 4'-methyl-4-phenyl-8-methylpsoralene (Ia). By similar series of reactions, 4'-ethyl-4-phenyl-8-methylpsoralene (Ib) and 4',4-diphenyl-8-methylpsoralene (Ic) were synthesised from 7-hydroxy-6-propionyl-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-4-phenyl-8-methyl-coumarin. 4'-Alkyl or aryl-4,8-dimethylpsoralene derivatives were also synthesised by carrying out a similar series of reactions starting with 7-hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin.

The study of the photodynamic activity of these psoralene derivatives by FMN method developed by Musajo and Rodighiero⁷ is in progress, the results of which will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Hydroxy-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin : 2-Methyl resorcinol (12.4 g.; 0.1M) and ethyl benzoylacetate (19.2 g.; 0.1M) are mixed and cooled in an ice bath. The mixture is then slowly added to con. sulphuric acid (29.4 g.; 0.3M) kept in an ice bath. The reaction mixture was left overnight and was poured on crushed ice. The compound was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 244°. Yield 9 g. (Found : C, 76.19; H, 4.22%. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.20; H, 4.65%).

7-Acyloxy-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin derivatives : 7-Hydroxy-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin derivative (2 g.) was acetylated by refluxing it with acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and con. sulphuric acid (2-3 drops) for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water. The product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide. It was crystallised from acetic acid. M.P., yields etc., of 7-acyloxy-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

7-Acyloxy-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarins

-8-methylcoumarin	M.P. °C	Crystn. solvent	Yield (g)	Formula	Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %
7-Acetoxy-4-phenyl	140	Acetic acid	1.5	$C_{18}H_{14}O_4$	73.56	73.48	4.62	4.78
7-Propionoxy-4-phenyl	109	,,	1.3	$C_{18}H_{16}O_4$	74.22	74.01	5.12	5.19
7-Benzoyloxy-4-phenyl	181	,,	1.6	$C_{23}H_{16}O_4$	77.56	77.54	4.43	4.49
7-Propionoxy-4-methyl	129	Ethanol	1.5	$C_{14}H_{14}O_4$	68.1	68.3	5.44	5.73
7-Benzoyloxy-4-methyl	213	Acetic acid	0.8	$C_{18}H_{14}O_4$	73.1	73.5	4.96	4.80

7-Hydroxy-6-acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin derivatives : An intimate mixture of 7-acyloxy-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin derivative (2 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (8 g.) was heated at 160° for 2 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice cold dil.HCl (1 : 1). The product was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid. M.P., yields etc., of 7-hydroxy-6-acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarin derivatives are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

7-Hydroxy-6-acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methylcoumarins

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl coumarin	M.P. °C	Crystn. solvent	Yield (g)	Formula	Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %
6-Acetyl-4-phenyl	203	Acetic acid	1.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄	73.56	73.48	4.41	4.78
6-Propionyl-4-phenyl	179	..	1.1	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	73.74	74.01	4.93	5.19
6-Benzoyl-4-phenyl	214	..	1.4	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	77.23	77.54	4.68	4.49
6-Propionyl-4-methyl	200	..	1.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄	67.9	68.3	5.46	5.73
6-Benzoyl-4-methyl	209	..	1.1	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄	73.1	73.5	4.81	4.80

A general process for the synthesis of ethyl-8-methyl-6-acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-7-coumarinoxy acetate : *o*-Hydroxy ketones described in Table II (1 g.), ethylbromoacetate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) were refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) for 4-5 hrs. in water bath. The acetone was evaporated and the residue was treated with water. The compound was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The esters were crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid and are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Ethyl-8-methyl-6-acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-7-coumarinoxyacetates

8-Methyl-7-coumarinoxy- acetate	M.P. °C	Crystn. solvent	Yield (g)	Formula	Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %
Ethyl-6-acetyl-4-phenyl	100-1	Alcohol	0.8	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	70.00	69.47	5.47	5.29
Ethyl-6-propionyl-4-phenyl	180-1	..	0.7	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₆	70.14	70.04	5.68	5.58
Ethyl-6-benzoyl-4-phenyl	133	..	0.7	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₆	72.83	73.29	5.06	4.97
Ethyl-6-acetyl-4-methyl	123	Acetic acid	0.7	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₆	64.1	64.1	6.05	5.70
Ethyl-6-propionyl-4-methyl	130	..	0.6	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₆	65.5	65.0	6.29	6.07
Ethyl-6-benzoyl-4-methyl	131	..	0.7	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	69.1	69.5	5.80	5.30

Hydrolysis of the above esters to the corresponding acids : The ester (1 g.) was hydrolysed by leaving it overnight with sodium hydroxide (25 cc.; 10%). The solution was filtered and the filtrate on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid afforded the required acid, which was purified by taking it in sodium bicarbonate solution. The acids were crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid and are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

6-Acyl-4-alkyl or aryl-8-methyl-7-coumarinoxyacetic acids

-8-Methyl-7-coumarinoxy-acetic acid	M.P. °C	Crystn. solvent	Yield (g)	Formula	Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %
6-Acetyl-4-phenyl	202	Alcohol	0.7	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	68.11	69.19	4.43	4.54
6-Propionyl-4-phenyl	149-50	„	0.6	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₆	70.15	70.46	5.2	4.92
6-Benzoyl-4-phenyl	184	„	0.6	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₆	72.52	72.46	4.46	4.348
6-Acetyl-4-methyl	207	Acetic acid	0.5	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	61.6	62.1	4.92	4.86
6-Propionyl-4-methyl	184	„	0.6	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₆	63.0	63.1	5.45	5.27
6-Benzoyl-4-methyl	199	„	0.2	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	67.7	68.2	4.85	4.58

Cyclisation of the acid to the psoralene derivatives : The above acid (0.5 g.) was mixed with acetic anhydride (4 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1 g.). The mixture was refluxed gently on sand bath for 2-3 hr. The reaction mixture, after cooling was added to ice water. The compound was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove acid. The psoralene derivatives were crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid and are recorded in the Table V.

TABLE V

4,4',8-alkyl or aryl psoralenes

Compound	M.P. °C	Crystn. solvent	Yield (g)	Formula	Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %
Ia	151	Alcohol	0.2	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	78.28	78.6	4.69	4.83
Ib	161-2	„	0.2	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃	77.99	78.43	5.11	5.23
Ic	244	Acetic acid	0.3	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₃	82.1	81.8	4.99	4.58
Id	183	„	0.25	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	74.1	73.7	5.53	5.30
Ie	142	Ethanol	0.10	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	74.6	74.4	5.97	5.78
If	198	„	0.10	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	78.3	78.6	5.23	4.85

TABLE VI

Ultra-violet absorption spectra of psoralene derivatives

Compound	Methanol max (log e)	Methanol max (log e)	Methanol max (log e)
Ia	225 (3.89)	253 (4.60)	307 (3.75)
Ib	225 (3.80)	255 (4.45)	310 (3.72)
Ic	222 (3.82)	254 (4.28)	307 (4.01)
Id	220 (3.87)	248 (4.63)	298 (4.28)
Ie	220 (3.80)	249 (4.50)	299 (4.19)
If	222 (3.89)	250 (4.43)	299 (4.18)

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